

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon MSCA Staff Exchange 2022 program under the grant agreement 1011361612.

Ref. Ares(2024)8261209 - 20/11/2024

Project: 1011361612 – SameMultiPhys –HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters in The Same Cell

DELIVERABLE D8.2 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Due Date of Deliverable	M6	Completion Date of Deliverable	20/11/2024
Deliverable leading partner	UPM	Author	Blanca González
Signed off by		Person	Gustavo R. Plaza
WP no.	WP8	WP Title	Dissemination and Communication
Dissemination level	Public		

Start date of the project	01/11/2024	Duration	48 months
----------------------------------	------------	-----------------	-----------

Version	V1.0	Status	Final Version
Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. No.	Author	Change

Coordinator:

Participants (3):

Partners (4):

Table of Contents

List of figures and tables	4
1. Introduction	5
1.1 Objectives of the data management plan (DMP).....	5
2. Data summary	6
2.1 Re-use of existing data.....	6
2.2 Types and formats of data.....	6
2.2.1 Type: sensitive vs. public data.....	6
2.2.2 Formats of data	8
2.3 Purpose of data generation	8
2.4 Expected data volume.....	9
2.5 Origin/provenance of data	10
2.6 Data utility.....	10
3. FAIR research data management	11
3.1 Making data findable	11
3.1.1 Persistent identifiers	11
3.1.2 Metadata parameters.....	12
3.1.3 Search optimization	12
3.1.4 Indexing.....	12
3.2 Making data accessible	12
3.2.1 Repositories.....	12
3.2.2 Access restrictions.....	12
3.2.3 Free access protocols.....	13
3.2.4 Metadata accessibility.....	13
3.2.5 Data availability period.....	13
3.3 Making data interoperable	13
3.2.1 Standards and vocabularies	13
3.4 Increasing data re-use.....	13
3.2.1 Documentation	13
3.2.2 Licenses	13
3.2.3 Provenance and quality assurance.....	13
4. Other research outputs	14
4.1 Digital outputs.....	14
4.2 Physical outputs	14
5. Allocation of resources	15
5.1 Costs	15
5.2 Coverage.....	15
5.3 Responsibility	15
5.4 Preservation	15
6. Data security.....	16

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon-MSCA
Staff Exchange 2022 program under the grant agreement 1011361612.

6.1 Provisions.....	16
6.2 Trusted repositories.....	16
7. Ethics	17
8. Conclusions	18

List of figures and tables

	Page
Figure 1. SameMultiPhys's Zenodo community, a trusted OPENAIRE's repository for all types of data	11
Table 1. Deliverables of SameMultiPhys, classified by dissemination level.	7
Table 2. Type of data and formats of SameMultiPhys project	13

1

Introduction

The scope of the first version of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to define key elements that will facilitate the potential reuse of the data collected and processed during and after the SameMultiPhys project. The DMP will ensure that the project's data is '*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*' given the objectives and scope of the project, following findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable principles (FAIR), but to keep as closed as necessary to protect Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

1.1 Objectives of the data management plan (DMP)

This document is the initial SameMultiPhys Data Management Plan. The DMP identifies the datasets that will be generated and used during the project and defines each dataset's purpose and life cycle. In accordance with Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016), the objectives of the SameMultiPhys's DMP are:

- To identify the datasets that SameMultiPhys will produce.
- To define how these datasets will be made 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
- To define the allocation of resources (costs and responsibility) for data management during and after the project.
- To define procedures for data security (including data recovery as well as safe storage) during the project and for long term preservation.

The Deliverable 8.2 "Data Management Plan" is part of work package 8 "Dissemination and Communication" and has been developed following the Horizon Europe guidelines. The DMP is intended to be a living document where information will be continuously added and revised as the implementation progresses.

As key element of sustainable data management, the DMP outlines what, and how, data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access and also how data will be curated and preserved during and after the end of the project. It provides guidelines, answers to issues, and presents the approach that the SameMultiPhys project will adopt with respect to the management and protection of data. Legal and ethical issues related to the project's collecting and/or processing of personal data are identified and practically considered, taking into consideration the different methods by which data are collected.

The intended target for this DMP is primarily constituted by the project partners. It is the responsibility of each partner to notify the coordinator of changes in the data they are collecting during the project.

The structure of this document is based on the template '[EU Grants: Data management plan \(HE\): V1.1 – 01.04.2022](#)', a report facilitated by the European Commission on 12 October, 2023.

2

Data summary

2.1 Re-use of existing data

It is very likely that no existing data of other projects will be re-used in SameMultiPhys for several reasons: (a) Methodological differences: SameMultiPhys involves developing entirely new methodologies to measure multiple parameters on the same cell, prototypes and datasets, and there is limited compatibility with previous datasets focused on multiple measurements on different populations of cells; (b) Project timeline: SameMultiPhys is at an early stage, focused on the design and fabrication of new microfluidic tools, thus the use of existing data does not yet align with project's needs; (c) Ethical and legal constraints: intellectual property, industrial privacy concerns of microfluidics companies limit access to or reuse of data from similar projects.

2.2 Types and formats of data

2.2.1 Type: sensitive vs. public data

Table 1 provides a summary of the project's 18 deliverables, classified by work-package and dissemination level.

Eight deliverables (44% of the total) were classified as 'sensitive' in terms of dissemination level, specifically, those related to the exploitation of the results of work packages WP2 (Design and Fabrication of Prototypes) and WP3 (Standardizing Measurements with Calibration Samples), as they can possibly lead to patent(s) application. Considering the above, protection to sensitive data related with WP2 and WP3 will be ensured in the project, for issues pertaining to the exploitation plan for commercialization of project's results.

In contrast, ten deliverables (56% of the total) were classified as 'public', ensuring their accessibility to the broader scientific and industrial communities. These deliverables include those from WP1 (Management), WP4 (Testing and Validating Prototypes), and WP5 (Quantifying images and performing statistical analysis), WP6 (Refine: evaluation of the prototypes for improvements) and WP7 (Development of Biophysical Models of Cell Response). The public deliverables aim to enhance transparency, foster collaboration, and maximize the impact of the project by sharing knowledge and tools in open-access journals.

This classification highlights the balanced data-sharing strategy outlined in the SameMultiPhys DMP:

- **Sensitive data**: Information critical for exploitation and commercialization will be carefully safeguarded to protect intellectual property and ensure successful outcomes for the project.
- **Public data**: Wherever possible, data will be made open and accessible to foster knowledge exchange and maximize the project's impact on the broader scientific and industrial communities.

Table 1 – Deliverables of SameMultiPhys, classified by dissemination level.

Work Package No	Work Package	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable Name	Type	Dissemination Level
WP1	Management	D1.1	Handbook on management	Report	PUBLIC
WP4	Testing and Validating Prototypes	D4.1	Report of the results of calibration methodology verification	Report	PUBLIC
WP4	Testing and Validating Prototypes	D4.2	Report of the results of verification using cell lines	Report	PUBLIC
WP5	Quantifying images and performing statistical analysis	D5.1	Report of analysis of image data, including technical data analysis	Report	PUBLIC
WP5	Quantifying images and performing statistical analysis	D5.2	Scripts to perform automatic analysis of acquired data	OTHER	PUBLIC
WP6	Refine: evaluation of the prototypes for improvements	D6.1	Report of quality analysis and results of verification in the refined prototype	Report	PUBLIC
WP7	Development of Biophysical Models of Cell Response	D7.1	Report of numerical analysis model	Report	PUBLIC
WP7	Development of Biophysical Models of Cell Response	D7.2	Outline of the biophysical biomarkers identified, and related potential meaningful relationships in the data	Report	PUBLIC
WP8	Dissemination and Communication	D8.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan and Communication "toolkit"	Report	PUBLIC
WP8	Dissemination and Communication	D8.2	Data Management Plan	DMP	PUBLIC
WP1	Management	D1.2	Progress report	Report	SENSITIVE
WP1	Management	D1.3	Mid-term meeting	Report	SENSITIVE
WP2	Design and Fabrication of Prototypes	D2.1	Design of microfluidic system to perform multiparameter, biophysical and same-cell assays	Demonstrator	SENSITIVE
WP2	Design and Fabrication of Prototypes	D2.2	Technical parameters of the fabrication process of microfluidic devices	Report	SENSITIVE
WP2	Design and Fabrication of Prototypes	D2.3	100 units of microfluidic system to perform multiparameter for prototype testing	DEM	SENSITIVE
WP3	Standardizing Measurements with Calibration Samples	D3.1	Report of the calibration samples to perform standardizing measurements	Report	SENSITIVE
WP3	Standardizing Measurements with Calibration Samples	D3.2	Protocol for the fabrication and biofunctionalization of calibration samples	Report	SENSITIVE
WP8	Dissemination and Communication	D8.3	Exploitation Plan	Report	SENSITIVE

2.2.2 Formats of data

The project will generate in the work packages (WP) 1-8 the type and formats of Table 1. Regardless of the sensitive vs. public nature of the data, researchers of the project will be advised to use the 'Recommended format' referred to in Table 2 to decide the best file formats.

Table 2 – Type of data and formats of SameMultiPhys project

Type of data	Recommended format	Acceptable formats
1. Tabular data with minimal metadata Column headings, variable names	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comma-separated values (.csv) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delimited text (.txt) with characters not present in data used as delimiters Widely-used formats: MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb) Statistics data (RDATA) Matlab format
2. Textual data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rich text Format (.rtf) Plain text, ASCII (.txt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx)
3. Design data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Autodesk Inventor 2023 format (.ipt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Autodesk Inventor 2023 format (.ipt) CleWin4 formats : (.cif), (.dxf)
4. Image data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TIFF 6.0 uncompressed (.tif) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg) if original created in this format GIF (.gif) PNG Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF.pdf)
5. Video data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPEG-4 (.mp4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AVI (.avi)
6. Documentation and scripts for analysis/instrumentation software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rich Text Format (.rtf) PDF/UA, PDF/A or PDF (.pdf) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plain text (.txt) Widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF.pdf) Python and Matlab Formats LabView format

2.3 Purpose of data generation

The data collection and generation within SameMultiPhys aim to optimize microfluidic tools for measuring multiple biophysical parameters in single cells, ensuring alignment with the project's objectives.

2.4 Expected data volume

Over the duration of the project, approximately 2 TB of raw and processed data is expected to be generated, based on the data types outlined in Section 2.2. Below is a detailed breakdown of how this volume could accumulate:

- 1. Raw and processed tabular data:** Experimental data from high-throughput microfluidic experiments is a significant contributor. Each experiment may produce several megabytes to gigabytes of data, depending on factors like sampling rate, duration, and the number of parameters measured. Repeated experiments across different work packages (WPs) will further increase the data volume.
- 2. Textual data:** Documentation of experimental protocols, annotations, and descriptive metadata will contribute to the total volume, though the size is generally smaller compared to other data types.
- 3. Design data:** Files for microfluidic device and component designs are relatively compact compared to imaging or video data but can still accumulate to several gigabytes due to iterative design processes and storage of multiple file versions.
- 4. Raw and processed imaging data:** Imaging data is typically the largest contributor. High-resolution images, such as microscopy files in TIFF format, range from tens to hundreds of megabytes per file. With multiple experimental conditions and runs, the cumulative size of imaging data is projected to exceed 1 TB.
- 5. Video data:** Video data, including high-definition or time-lapse recordings (e.g., AVI format), is another major contributor. Individual videos can range from hundreds of megabytes to several gigabytes. Cumulatively, video data is also expected to surpass 0.5 TB.
- 6. Documentation and scripts for analysis/instrumentation software:** Computational simulations, such as finite element modeling, produce extensive datasets, including raw output files, visualizations, and logs. The size of these files can range from tens of megabytes to several gigabytes per simulation run. Instrumentation software files, though generally smaller, may accumulate to several gigabytes over multiple revisions and test cases. Additionally, textual and presentation documentation, while lightweight individually, can add up to several gigabytes with extensive documentation practices.

Overall Estimation

- 1. Raw and Processed Experimental Data:** ~100 GB
- 2. Textual Data:** ~40 GB
- 3. Design Data:** ~10 GB
- 4. Raw and Processed Imaging Data:** ~1 TB
- 5. Video Data:** ~650 GB
- 6. Documentation and Scripts for Analysis/Instrumentation Software:** ~200 GB

The cumulative volume (~2 TB) considers not only the individual contributions of data types but also redundancy (e.g., backups, intermediate processing steps), collaboration-related file exchanges, and project duration.

2.5 Origin/provenance of data

- Generated from experimental setups within the consortium's laboratories.
- Computational models developed using in-house and collaborative methodologies.
- Documentation of the prototypes fabricated for microfluidic analyses.
- Deliverables of the project.

2.6 Data utility

Outside of the project, the generated data may be relevant for researchers in mechanobiology, bioengineering, and related fields. Additionally, it may be relevant to industrial stakeholders supporting biomarkers' discovery.

3

FAIR research data management

Effective Research Data Management (RDM) is a cornerstone of responsible and high-quality research. It provides a structured framework for organizing, storing, and sharing data in ways that promote transparency, reproducibility, and compliance with ethical and legal standards. Central to RDM is the adoption of the FAIR principles—ensuring that research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. These principles not only support the ethos of Open Science but also enable collaboration, foster innovation, and maximize the value of research outputs. This chapter explores the fundamental aspects of SameMultiPhys's FAIR-aligned RDM, including the selection of appropriate licenses, the use of trusted repositories, and strategies for ensuring long-term accessibility and usability of data. By adhering to these practices, SameMultiPhys' researchers will enhance the impact and integrity of their work while meeting the growing expectations of the scientific community.

3.1 Making data findable

3.1.1 Persistent identifiers

All datasets will be assigned DOIs through repositories via **Zenodo**, a general-purposed repository for all outcomes of the project, (<https://zenodo.org/>). Specifically, a community in Zenodo will be used to share and preserve SameMultiPhys's deliverables, publications, data and software for free in OpenAIRE's trusted repository hosted by CERN. The URL of the SameMultiPhys's Zenodo community is: <https://zenodo.org/communities/samemultiphys/>.

Figure 1. SameMultiPhys's Zenodo community, a trusted OPENAIRE's repository for all types of data

3.1.2 Metadata parameters

Metadata summarises basic information about data, which can make future data analysis more effective and efficient. In SameMultiPhys, all data will have an associated metadata document (stored as a .txt file) which describes key aspects of the data, including at least the following fields:

- Author(s) name
- Author(s) ORCID
- DOI
- Licence
- Language
- Journal (if applicable)
- Title
- Institution
- Date created
- Date last modified
- File format
- Comments
- Keywords
- Size
- Type

3.1.3 Search optimization

Keywords such as 'cell mechanics', 'microfluidics', and 'biophysical parameters', 'biomarkers' will be included in metadata for discoverability and re-use.

Filenames will include creation date in YYYYMMDD format. Deliverable reports will have a data identification sheet and version log.

3.1.4 Indexing

Metadata will be harvestable and indexed in OpenAIRE, which connects with Zenodo's repository.

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Repositories

All project data will be deposited in a trusted repository, Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/samemultiphys/>), which is compliant with OpenAIRE guidelines and provides long-term preservation and accessibility of research outputs.

3.2.2 Access restrictions

- **Public data:** Publicly shareable data will be accessible via Zenodo to all consortium partners and external stakeholders.

- **Sensitive data:** Sensitive data will also be hosted on Zenodo but with access restricted to project partners, in accordance with confidentiality agreements and intellectual property considerations.
- **Backup and restricted data:** An additional online copy of the data will be maintained in an institutional account at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, linked with a Google Drive account, to ensure secure storage and accessibility. Data with intellectual property or confidentiality concerns will be shared under restricted access or embargo periods as outlined in the Grant Agreement. or confidentiality concerns will be shared under restricted access or embargo, as per the Grant Agreement.

3. 2.3 Free access protocols

To comply with Horizon Europe requirements, publicly available data will be accessible via open access protocols, ensuring transparency and broad dissemination of research outputs.

3.2.4 Metadata accessibility

Metadata will be openly shared under CC0 licenses, making it freely accessible for reuse without restrictions. Metadata will include references to relevant software, computational tools, or workflows as needed, facilitating reproducibility and interoperability.

3.2.5 Data availability period

All data and metadata will be preserved and made accessible for a minimum of 10 years after the project's completion, ensuring long-term usability and compliance with best practices in data stewardship.

3.3 Making data interoperable

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP.

3.2.1 Standards and vocabularies

In the project we use standard file formats as noted above. Every dataset will have standard Zenodo metadata.

3.4 Increasing data re-use

3.2.1 Documentation

Each dataset will include comprehensive documentation (e.g., methodology, protocols, and variable definitions).

3.2.2 Licenses

Data will be licensed under **CC-BY** or similar reuse-friendly licenses.

3. 2.3 Provenance and quality assurance

Regular quality checks will ensure consistency and accuracy.

4

Other research outputs

4.1 Digital outputs

Software scripts (Python/MATLAB), workflows, and models will be shared under open-source licenses in Zenodo.

4.2 Physical outputs

Microfluidic prototypes and biological samples will be documented and shared with collaborators under specific agreements.

5

Allocation of resources

5.1 Costs

Cost for making data fair are estimated to be zero. Zenodo is funded by the EU, which means archiving data in this repository will be free of charge. Consortium partners will use their own budgets to archive a back-up copy of all data in their own repositories.

5.2 Coverage

Costs will be covered by the Horizon Europe grant.

5.3 Responsibility

The Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) will take the lead in data management, with a designated data manager responsible for overall coordination. Each Work Package leader will ensure that the datasets generated within their activities adhere to the FAIR principles. UPM, as the Project Coordinator, will share responsibility for the general oversight and supervision of data management activities. Additionally, all consortium partners are responsible for ensuring that their activities comply with applicable local, national, and international laws, regulations, and guidelines.

5.4 Preservation

Long-term storage will be ensured through Zenodo and institutional repositories.

6

Data security

6.1 Provisions

Data will be encrypted during transfer and storage. Backup protocols will include weekly snapshots to offsite servers.

6.2 Trusted repositories

Zenodo and institutional repositories will ensure long-term preservation.

7

Ethics

All data handling will adhere to the ethical standards outlined in the **Description of the Action (DoA)** of the project and the **Consortium Agreement (CA)**. These documents specify the ethical and legal framework for managing data throughout the project's duration, ensuring that the rights of all parties are respected, and the data is used responsibly. The main issues that can impact data sharing are:

- **Ownership and licensing:** Data generated during research may be subject to intellectual property laws. If a researcher or institution has patented a method, process, or product derived from the data, sharing it without proper licensing could infringe on IP rights.
- **Commercialization concerns:** Some data may contain commercially valuable information that could impact a company's competitive edge or violate trade secrets if shared improperly.

8

Conclusions

This report presents the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the SameMultiPhys project and reflects the status of the mandatory quality requirements. A delay in the submission of this deliverable was due an administrative delay in the signature of the Consortium Agreement; this DMP was only submitted once that the CA was signed by all parties.

The first iteration of the DMP outlines the strategies for promoting the project's findings throughout its duration. It ensures the transferability of relevant project information while adhering to the restrictions defined by the Consortium Agreement. Within this framework, the DMP lays the foundation for both the Dissemination Plan and the Exploitation Plan.

This version of the DMP will be regularly monitored and updated in parallel with the evolving Dissemination and Exploitation Plans. The progress of the DMP's implementation will be documented in the Project Progress Reports.

This document should be read in conjunction with all referenced materials, including the EC Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, annexes, and relevant guidelines.